

a-service support, and OpenCAPIF for secure API access. These initiatives, supported by several European projects, aim to build a comprehensive toolkit for advanced network deployment and management. Besides, several related groups are of interest towards 6G: Research, Innovation and Standards Ecosystem (RISE) group as well as the ETSI Technology Radar for Integrated Sensing and Communication. In 2024, the ITU’s IMT-2030 framework progressed by refining 6G requirements, emphasizing seamless connectivity, high bandwidth, ultra-low latency, and large-scale device support. Building on its 2023 approval, ITU is defining technical criteria and evaluation benchmarks through 2027. The framework supports immersive applications, intelligent networks, and broad coverage across diverse environments, while promoting energy efficiency and green technologies. Together, ITU and 3GPP efforts offer a cohesive path toward 6G, laying a strong foundation for the transition from 5G.

IV. PRE-STANDARDISATION ACTIVITIES IN THE 6G-IA

The 6G-IA Pre-Standardization Working Group (WG) supports alignment between SNS-JU projects and key regulatory bodies like ETSI, 3GPP, and ITU-R, contributing to a unified European 6G strategy. In 2024, a new standardization group was launched under the SNS-JU Policy WG to streamline priorities for 3GPP and address policy topics like security, sustainability, and EU autonomy. This subgroup, supported by both public and private sectors, began its work in October 2024 and plans bi-weekly meetings to identify key standardization areas and analyze the landscape using tools like IPlytics.

V. ANALYSIS OF CONTRIBUTIONS OF SNS PROJECTS TO STANDARDISATION BODIES

According to the survey to SNS projects run by SNS OPS and as shown in Figure 2, ETSI and 3GPP continue to be the most popular targets for contributions for Call 1 and 2 projects.

Figure 2: Contribution projects to standard bodies.

Interestingly, an increase can be observed in the contributions to O-RAN at the expense of those to the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF)/Internet Research Task Force IRTF. The majority of 3GPP contributions by SNS projects are aimed at the System Architecture (SA2) specification group due to the given 3GPP timeline and the planned workshop in March 2025, which will focus on core network and system aspects. The high number of contributions to O-RAN Radio Intelligent Controller Workgroup (WG3, WG2) and ETSI Zero-touch

network and Service Management (ISG ZSM) can be similarly explained, as they strongly relate to system aspects at this stage. As for open-source contributions to WGs in standardization bodies and open-source projects, its number has substantially increased from only 23 in Call 1 to 67 open-source contributions in Call 2 projects. Most of these contributions, 28, are geared towards radio access networks (Open-RAN, OpenAirInterface, SRSRAN). In the first call, in total 132 open-source solutions were used. The top-ranked open-source solutions which projects made use of are: in the core (e.g. Open5GS, FreeGC), cloud (e.g., Kubernetes, Docker), followed by smaller areas Radio, Support Systems.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Standardization is essential for interoperability and global competitiveness, with a strong push toward a unified 6G standard. Key organizations are aligning on spectrum, architecture, and societal impacts to support a resilient global 6G ecosystem. Major efforts are underway in 3GPP and ETSI, with milestones like 3GPP Release 20 (2025) and Release 21 (2030), and ETSI initiatives on Terahertz and Zero-touch Networks. Europe is taking a leading role, collaborating with ITU, ETSI, and 3GPP, and contributing through 6G-IA’s pre-standardization group and the SNS-JU Policy WG. SNS projects increasingly contribute to both standards and open-source efforts, especially in core network and system areas.

To sustain Europe’s leadership in telecom and maximize its 6G standardization impact, stakeholders must take a coordinated, proactive approach. Based on this paper’s analysis, SNS ICE offers tailored **recommendations**. The **SNS Office, public sector, and policymakers** should strengthen support for standardization by encouraging systematic participation in ITU, 3GPP, and ETSI, and incentivizing EU-funded R&I projects to contribute to global standards. For the **telecom industry**, active engagement in international standardization is key to influencing 6G specs, with early attention to end-user needs. **Academia and SMEs** should lead or support pre-standardization in areas like spectrum sharing and low-power communication. **Cross-sector coordination** is vital to ensure strong European representation and leadership in global 6G efforts.

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